

ISic1294

I.Sicily inscription 1294

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140784

1. ἐνθάδ[ε κείται Διο]-

2. νυσία. [χρηστή καὶ]

3. ἄμεν π [τε χαῖρε].

4.

Edition: PHI140785

1. ἐνθάδ[ε κίτε Διο]-

2. νυσία [ζήσασα]

3. ἀμένπ [τωσ ἔτη —]

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492898

EDCS 39101663

PHI 140784

PHI 140785

Bibliography

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